

European long-term ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological systems research
infrastructure PLUS

Project-specific informational material

Deliverable D6.4

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 University of Helsinki, Finland
<https://www.lter-europe.net/projects/elter-plus>

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Preface & Summary

To achieve successful communication and dissemination of results, a recognisable project identity was created for eLTER PLUS and a number of promotional tools and materials were produced. As part of the communication strategy, both offline and online dissemination of eLTER PLUS will take place with the goal to reach a broader audience.

This report describes the process of creation of means for successful dissemination, communication and knowledge transfer as well as future plans for materials and tools.

1. The eLTER PLUS branding identity

1.1 Project logo

As part of the project branding development for eLTER PLUS as a distinguishable entity, which is still following the aesthetics of eLTER, it was decided that all eLTER projects and products will be based on the main eLTER logo (Fig 1), while the differing elements will be distinguished by a specific colour.

Figure 1. The central eLTER logo

As a result of this strategy a new logo (Fig. 2) was designed for eLTER PLUS to serve as a recognisable visual element and set the aesthetics of future eLTER PLUS visual materials, including colour-coding of new webpages, news labels, brochures, posters, infographs etc.

Figure 2. eLTER PLUS project logo

The logo was created in the following formats (vector and non vector) to make sure partners can find a suitable version regardless of the type of material they need it for: .eps, .jpg, .png, .pdf, .svg.

A long version of the logo featuring the full eLTER title was also designed and is available in the same formats to be used in the cases where necessary (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. eLTER PLUS logo, full spelling version

1.2 Colour scheme

Based on the overall colour scheme inbuilt in the eLTER logo as a guiding principle for the project materials the following colour scheme will be used to maintain consistent identity.

HEX

#b8e0ff	#ff9900	#92d050	#00579a
#008080			

As a tool to make PLUS distinguishable from other visual communication materials the following colour was adopted as signature for PLUS.

Signature colour:

#008080

2 eLTER PLUS information material

2.1 Current progress

Up until month 6 a dedicated project flyer was created, alongside an update of the overall eLTER brochure to feature information of the project. Additionally, due to the COVID-19 crisis and great number of events that were moved online a decision was taken to create an eLTER virtual booth, using Prezi as a tool, where the project was prominently featured. A template was created for deliverables to ensure consistent reporting to the EC and to provide identity to public ones.

2.1.1 Project flyer

The eLTER PLUS flyer was designed in a way to visually capture the attention of the reader and increase awareness of the project. It explains the rationale behind the project – its objectives, the activities and main tasks planned as well as the expected results (Fig. 4). The flyer was created to reflect the conceptual design of the project logo and website.

eLTER PLUS

**INTEGRATED EUROPEAN
LONG-TERM ECOSYSTEM, CRITICAL
ZONE AND SOCIO-ECOLOGICAL
RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE PLUS**

The eLTER Advanced Community Project (eLTER PLUS) tests the performance and further develops the services of the emerging eLTER Research Infrastructure (eLTER RI), together with RI users from several research communities.

CASE STUDIES

ADDRESSING IMPORTANT RESEARCH CHALLENGES

In its exemplary case studies, eLTER PLUS studies ecosystem and socio-ecological responses to globally critical environmental challenges, which are endangering ecosystem integrity and ecosystem services. This involves creating new tools for cross-disciplinary collaboration, improving access to selected sites and platforms in terrestrial, freshwater and coastal ecosystems, and facilitating the use of their long-term observational data.

Embedded in a holistic approach, each of the case studies focuses on one research challenge:

- Biodiversity loss
- Biogeochemical controls of ecosystem functions
- Climate-water-food nexus
- Socio-ecological systems

WWW.LTER-EUROPE.NET/PROJECTS/PLUS

This project receives funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 871128.

STRENGTHENING THE COMMUNITY

eLTER PLUS will further open and expand the developing RI by engaging current and new users from academia, civil society and industry. The project will challenge, assess and strengthen the operations of the eLTER RI through engaging the best expertise and sites available for integrated ecosystem research. eLTER PLUS will:

- scout for innovative observation and analytical methods to be implemented across the RI and to support its sustainable operations
- offer an excellent training program for site operators, researchers and students to enhance their capacities in ecosystem research
- further integrate the operations of advanced *in-situ*, inter- and transdisciplinary research, inter alia by prioritizing Standard Observation variables
- develop pilots for IT services and tools according to user priorities systematically collected across the four research challenges
- create "information clusters" by integrating data from eLTER sites with other data and information retrieved from a wide range of sources

Within eLTER PLUS, up to 100 selected sites from LTER-Europe will provide access to data and knowledge to researchers and environmental managers:

- 35 sites will offer transnational access to users through visits, training and remote access provided by site personnel.
- More than 50 sites will offer virtual access to long-term data.

PROJECT COORDINATION AND CONTACT

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CONSORTIUM
33 partners from across 23 countries

DURATION
1 Feb 2020 – 31 Jan 2025

Subscribe to the eLTER Newsletter here:

Figure 4. eLTER PLUS project flyer

Additionally, information about the newly started project was added to the overall eLTER brochure to underline the importance of the project for the development of the eLTER RI (Fig. 5). The project flyer is designed to work both as a separate material and as an inlay in the overall eLTER tri-fold brochure.

CENTRAL SERVICES

A range of centrally-provided services will make eLTER RI more than the sum of its national networks. These Central Services are expected to consist of:

- **Head office:** coordination, strategic development, outreach. Head office activities are currently hosted by UFZ, Germany.
- **eLTER Service Portal:** access to data and sites
- **Topic Centres:** covering Quality Assurance for Data, Modelling and Analysis Tools, Design and Synthesis, and Technological Innovation and Development.

Central Services: Head Office, Topic Centres, Service Portal (single access point), eLTER Platforms, eLTER Sites, National Research Infrastructures.

Services for USERS

- Research site access
- Long-term in-situ data (EEVs: legacy, recent)
- Integration of data from various sources (RS, sat. statistics, modelling, mapping) & analytical tools
- High-level data products tailored to inform policy
- Research project design support
- Research technology/R&D
- Education & training

SUPPORTING PROJECTS

Starting in 2020, the provision, testing and development of the eLTER RI will be supported by two EU-funded large scale international projects:

eLTER PPP The eLTER RI will be further developed within the 5-year Preparatory Phase Project (eLTER PPP), coordinated by the Helmholtz-Centre for Environmental Research (UFZ) in Germany. www.lter-europe.net/services/PPP

eLTER PLUS The Advanced Community Project, eLTER PLUS, coordinated by the University of Helsinki in Finland, will conduct a performance test of the emerging eLTER RI, challenging, assessing and strengthening its operations through scientific case studies and pilot service developments. www.lter-europe.net/projects/PLUS

OUR MISSION
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TAKING THE PULSE OF EUROPE'S ENVIRONMENTAL SYSTEM

www.lter-europe.net

Figure 5. eLTER overall flyer featuring new information about the project

2.1.2 eLTER virtual booth

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic and the cancellations or online format of most events that were planned during the first six months of the project duration, a situation likely to last for at least another six months until the end of 2020, a decision was taken to follow an innovative approach and create an online booth for eLTER and its projects.

The booth was created in Prezi (Fig. 6) and gives visitors the opportunity to click through various topics presented in an engaging way, visualise and download important materials, watch videos and find contact information or links to social media, newsletter etc.

Figure 6: Elements and overall experience of the eLTER virtual booth

2.1.3 Deliverable template

Deliverable corporate identity templates were designed in the very beginning of the project to make sure all project partners use a consistent visual presentation on eLTER PLUS -related reports. The template is specifically tailored to the information the document is required to contain. The template incorporates the eLTER PLUS project logo and suggests the information necessary to be included, as well as features important Grant information to ensure that finding is properly acknowledged.

2.2 Future steps

Additional branded communication materials will be created as required with the development of eLTER PLUS and the appearance of first project result, these include but are not limited to:

- Posters
- Updates of the flyer, or additional product specific flyers
- Infographics
- Factsheets
- Policy briefs
- Videos

3 Social media presence, press releases and other public statements

During the first six months of the project duration eLTER PLUS has maintained online presence through a number of channels and in accordance with the principles and plans outlined in Milestone 14 Project communication plan (finished in April 2020).

3.1 Social media

eLTER PLUS was featured and represented via the eLTER Twitter account through introductory posts, outlining the main features of the project and linking to further reading (Fig. 7). The eLTER Twitter account is enjoying an audience of 1,095 followers.

Figure 7: Example tweet introducing a crucial project milestone - the kick-off meeting of eLTER PLUS

3.2 Press releases

An introductory press release presenting the two new eLTER projects starting February, 2020 (eLTER PLUS and eLTER PPP) has been published and sent to key contacts to raise awareness in the community and pave the way towards successful project communication. Link: <https://www.lter-europe.net/news/elter-ppp-plus>

3.3 eLTER statement on COVID-19

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic the eLTER PLUS kick-off meeting was held fully online. During the meeting, the community discussed the implications of the coronavirus situations, as well as the importance and potential roles of environmental RIs in such situations of crisis. As a result, the eLTER statement on COVID-19 was published on the website and sent to eLTER's newsletter subscribers. Link: <https://www.lter-europe.net/covid-19-statement>

4 Conclusions

Deliverable 6.4 introduces the eLTER PLUS branding identity and the materials currently developed following the established look and feel. The deliverable also gives indication of future plans. All materials developed after this deliverable will be featured on the eLTER website and duly reported in the planned periodic reports.